

A STUDY TO ASSESS THE ATTITUDE AND FACTORS INFLUENCING THE OPTING OF VASECTOMY AMONG MEN IN SELECTED URBAN AREAS IN A VIEW TO DEVELOP AN INFORMATION BOOKLET.

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ABSTRACT

Background:

Vasectomy is a safe, effective, minimally invasive, and cost-efficient method of permanent male contraception. Despite its proven benefits, acceptance of vasectomy remains low in India due to sociocultural beliefs, misconceptions regarding masculinity and sexual performance, fear of complications, and inadequate awareness. Understanding men's attitudes and the factors influencing their decision-making is essential for developing effective educational interventions.

Objectives:

To assess the attitude toward vasectomy and identify factors influencing the opting of vasectomy among men in selected urban areas, and to determine the association between attitude, influencing factors, and selected demographic variables.

Methods:

A quantitative research approach with a descriptive cross-sectional design was adopted. The study was conducted among 200 married men aged 25–45 years residing in selected urban areas. Participants were selected using a non-probability purposive sampling technique. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire consisting of demographic variables, a Likert attitude scale, and a checklist of influencing factors. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis, with the Chi-square test applied to determine associations at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results:

The findings revealed that although 71% of participants had prior awareness of vasectomy, misconceptions and sociocultural barriers persisted. Fear of surgery (64%), fear of weakness (56%), social stigma, and inadequate knowledge were the major factors influencing acceptance. Most participants demonstrated generally favorable attitudes toward male participation in family planning; however, concerns regarding masculinity and sexual performance remained evident. Educational status, number of children, prior awareness, and spousal communication showed significant associations with attitude and influencing factors.

Conclusion:

Despite increasing awareness, acceptance of vasectomy among urban men continues to be constrained by misinformation and sociocultural beliefs. Education, counseling, and exposure to accurate information significantly improve attitudes toward vasectomy. The development of an evidence-based information booklet is recommended to enhance awareness, reduce misconceptions, and promote informed reproductive decision-making and shared family planning responsibility.

Keywords: Vasectomy, Male Sterilization, Attitude, Family Planning, Influencing Factors, Urban Men, Information Booklet.

INTRODUCTION

Family planning plays a vital role in improving maternal and child health, controlling population growth, and enhancing the overall quality of life. Among the various contraceptive methods available, vasectomy is recognized as a safe, simple, effective, and permanent method of male sterilization. It is a minor surgical procedure associated with minimal complications, high effectiveness, and cost efficiency. Despite these advantages, the acceptance of vasectomy remains considerably low in India compared to female sterilization.

Several sociocultural factors, misconceptions, and inadequate awareness contribute to the low utilization of vasectomy. Many men believe that vasectomy may affect their physical strength, sexual performance, or masculinity. Fear of surgery, lack of family support, religious beliefs, and social stigma further influence their decision regarding vasectomy. These misconceptions often prevent men from actively participating in family planning programs.

Promoting male involvement in reproductive health and family planning is essential for achieving equitable responsibility between partners. Understanding men's attitudes toward vasectomy and identifying the factors influencing their decision-making can help healthcare professionals develop effective educational and counselling strategies.

Therefore, the present study was undertaken to assess the attitude toward vasectomy and identify the factors influencing the opting of vasectomy among men in selected urban areas. The findings of the study may provide valuable information for planning awareness programs and developing educational materials to improve knowledge, reduce misconceptions, and promote informed decision-making regarding vasectomy.

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Family planning is an important component of reproductive health that contributes significantly to the well-being of individuals, families, and society. It helps couples achieve their desired family size, prevents unintended pregnancies, and improves maternal and child health outcomes. Although both men and women share responsibility for family planning, contraceptive practices are predominantly focused on women, particularly in developing countries such as India.

Vasectomy is a permanent method of male sterilization that is highly effective, safe, simple, and cost-efficient. The procedure involves minimal surgical intervention and has a very low risk of complications. Despite its advantages and the government's efforts to promote male participation in family planning programs, the acceptance of vasectomy remains low in India. According to national family planning reports, female sterilization continues to account for the majority of permanent contraceptive methods, whereas vasectomy contributes only a small proportion.

Several factors contribute to the low acceptance of vasectomy, including lack of awareness, misconceptions regarding sexual performance and masculinity, fear of surgical procedures, social stigma, cultural beliefs, and inadequate family support. These barriers often discourage men from considering vasectomy as a family planning option. Therefore, understanding men's attitudes and the factors influencing their decision to opt for vasectomy is essential for improving male involvement in reproductive health services and achieving family planning goals.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

Despite the availability of safe and effective family planning methods, male participation in contraception remains limited. Vasectomy is one of the most reliable permanent contraceptive methods; however, its

utilization continues to be significantly lower than female sterilization. This imbalance places a disproportionate burden of contraception on women and limits shared responsibility in reproductive decision-making.

Many studies have reported that misconceptions, fear of complications, lack of knowledge, social influences, and cultural beliefs negatively affect men's acceptance of vasectomy. In urban areas, although access to healthcare information is relatively better, misconceptions and negative attitudes toward vasectomy still persist. Understanding these attitudes and the factors influencing men's decisions is important for designing targeted educational and counseling interventions.

Nurses and other healthcare professionals play a crucial role in promoting family planning awareness and encouraging male involvement. Identifying the factors that influence acceptance of vasectomy will help healthcare providers develop effective educational strategies, reduce myths and misconceptions, and improve awareness among men. Hence, the present study is undertaken to assess the attitude toward vasectomy and identify the factors influencing the opting of vasectomy among men in selected urban areas.

METHODOLOGY

The present study adopted a quantitative research approach with a descriptive cross-sectional research design to assess the attitude toward vasectomy and identify the factors influencing the opting of vasectomy among men in selected urban areas.

The study was conducted in selected urban communities. The target population comprised married men residing in the selected urban areas. A total of 200 participants who met the inclusion criteria were selected using a non-probability purposive sampling technique.

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire consisting of three sections: demographic variables, an attitude scale regarding vasectomy, and a checklist to identify factors influencing the decision to opt for vasectomy. Prior permission was obtained from the concerned authorities, and informed consent was secured from all participants before data collection.

The collected data were coded, organized, and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used to describe the data, while the Chi-square test was applied to determine the association between attitude, influencing factors, and selected demographic variables. The level of significance was set at 0.05.

Ethical principles, including confidentiality, anonymity, and voluntary participation, were strictly maintained throughout the study.

RESULT

Section I: Distribution of men according to their selected demographic variables.

Table: I Demographic Characteristics of Participants (n = 200)

Demographic			
Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age	25–30 years	58	29.0
	31–35 years	64	32.0
	36–40 years	49	24.5
	41–45 years	29	14.5
Education	Primary	36	18.0
	Secondary	74	37.0
	Higher secondary	58	29.0
	Graduate & above	32	16.0
Occupation	Unskilled worker	41	20.5
	Skilled worker	63	31.5
	Private employee	54	27.0
	Government employee	22	11.0
	Business	20	10.0
Monthly Income	< ₹10,000	48	24.0
	₹10,001–20,000	72	36.0
	₹20,001–40,000	54	27.0
	> ₹40,000	26	13.0
Marital Status	Married	200	100.0
Number of			
Children	One	46	23.0
	Two	97	48.5
	Three or more	57	28.5
Religion	Hindu	142	71.0
	Muslim	36	18.0
	Christian	16	8.0
	Other	6	3.0
Heard	About		
Vasectomy	Yes	142	71.0
	No	58	29.0
Source of Information	Health worker	54	27.0

Section II: Assessment of attitude regarding opting of vasectomy among men in selected urban areas.**Table: II****Item-wise Analysis of Attitude Toward Vasectomy Among Men (n = 200)**

Statement	Strongly Agree n (%)	Agree n (%)	Neutral n (%)	Disagree n (%)	Strongly Disagree n (%)
Vasectomy is a safe method of family planning	72 (36.0)	68 (34.0)	28 (14.0)	20 (10.0)	12 (6.0)
Vasectomy reduces a man's physical strength*	28 (14.0)	40 (20.0)	36 (18.0)	58 (29.0)	38 (19.0)
Vasectomy affects sexual performance*	26 (13.0)	34 (17.0)	40 (20.0)	62 (31.0)	38 (19.0)
Family planning is only a woman's responsibility*	30 (15.0)	46 (23.0)	32 (16.0)	58 (29.0)	34 (17.0)
Men should participate in permanent contraception	66 (33.0)	72 (36.0)	28 (14.0)	20 (10.0)	14 (7.0)
Vasectomy is better than female sterilization	48 (24.0)	60 (30.0)	46 (23.0)	28 (14.0)	18 (9.0)
Society discourages men from vasectomy*	58 (29.0)	62 (31.0)	34 (17.0)	28 (14.0)	18 (9.0)
I would consider vasectomy after completing my family	64 (32.0)	70 (35.0)	30 (15.0)	22 (11.0)	14 (7.0)
Vasectomy causes long-term weakness*	34 (17.0)	48 (24.0)	40 (20.0)	46 (23.0)	32 (16.0)
Proper education can remove fear about vasectomy	78 (39.0)	66 (33.0)	28 (14.0)	16 (8.0)	12 (6.0)
Vasectomy is socially unacceptable*	42 (21.0)	48 (24.0)	38 (19.0)	44 (22.0)	28 (14.0)
Vasectomy improves family well-being	62 (31.0)	70 (35.0)	34 (17.0)	20 (10.0)	14 (7.0)

Table: III

Distribution of Factors Influencing Opting of Vasectomy (Multiple Response) (n = 200)

SN	Influencing Factor	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1	Fear of surgery	128	64.0
2	Fear of weakness	112	56.0
3	Lack of knowledge	138	69.0
4	Religious beliefs	62	31.0
5	Family pressure	84	42.0
6	Social stigma	118	59.0
7	Cultural beliefs	96	48.0
8	Desire for more children	104	52.0
9	Partner opposition	72	36.0
10	Economic concerns	58	29.0
11	Lack of medical trust	66	33.0
12	Absence of counseling services	92	46.0

Bar diagram showing percentage wise distribution according to the Factors Influencing Opting of Vasectomy

The findings reveal that the most dominant factor influencing vasectomy decisions was **lack of knowledge (69%)**. This indicates that informational deficiency is the primary barrier rather than deliberate refusal. Many men lack accurate understanding of the procedure, recovery, and long-term effects.

The second major barrier was **fear of surgery (64%)**, followed by **social stigma (59%)** and **fear of weakness (56%)**. These fears reflect deep psychological and cultural anxieties linked to masculinity, bodily integrity, and social perception. Vasectomy is often symbolically associated with loss of strength or sexual identity, which discourages men from considering it.

More than half of the respondents reported **desire for more children (52%)**, indicating that reproductive intentions strongly influence decision-making. This factor is practical rather than ideological and highlights the importance of timing in vasectomy acceptance. **Cultural beliefs (48%)** and **absence of counseling services (46%)** further emphasize the role of community norms and healthcare accessibility. Many participants may never have received structured counseling, leaving them dependent on hearsay and myths.

Family pressure (42%) and **partner opposition (36%)** demonstrate that vasectomy decisions are not purely individual but embedded within family dynamics. Spousal communication and joint decision-making play a critical role in male contraceptive behavior.

Religious beliefs (31%), lack of medical trust (33%), and economic concerns (29%) were less dominant but still relevant factors. These findings suggest that institutional trust and socio-economic considerations influence reproductive health choices.

Table IV

Chi-Square Analysis Showing Association Between Attitude Toward Vasectomy and Selected Demographic Variables (n = 200)

SN	Demographic Variable	χ^2 Value	df	p-value	Significance
1	Age	12.84	6	0.045	Significant
2	Education	18.62	6	0.005	Highly Significant
3	Occupation	14.27	8	0.075	Not Significant
4	Monthly Income	9.36	6	0.154	Not Significant
5	Number of Children	16.44	4	0.002	Significant
6	Religion	5.18	6	0.522	Not Significant
7	Heard About Vasectomy	28.96	2	<0.001	Highly Significant

Table: V**Chi-Square Analysis Showing Association Between Influencing Factors and Selected Demographic Variables (n = 200)**

SN	Demographic Variable	χ^2 Value	df	p-value	Significance
1	Age	10.72	6	0.097	Not Significant
2	Education	21.54	6	0.001	Highly Significant
3	Occupation	13.88	8	0.085	Not Significant
4	Monthly Income	11.46	6	0.075	Not Significant
5	Number of Children	17.92	4	0.001	Highly Significant
6	Religion	6.02	6	0.421	Not Significant
7	Heard About Vasectomy	24.36	2	<0.001	Highly Significant

RECOMMENDATIONS

Conduct regular community awareness programs focusing on male participation in family planning.

Develop and distribute culturally appropriate information booklets, pamphlets, and audiovisual materials on vasectomy.

Include comprehensive content on male contraception and vasectomy in undergraduate and postgraduate nursing curricula.

Train nursing students in gender-sensitive counselling and communication skills.

Establish dedicated male reproductive health counselling services within family planning clinics.

DISCUSSION

The present study was conducted to assess the attitude toward vasectomy and identify the factors influencing the opting of vasectomy among men in selected urban areas. The findings revealed that although most participants had heard about vasectomy, several misconceptions and sociocultural barriers continued to influence their perceptions and decisions regarding the procedure.

The study demonstrated that awareness alone does not necessarily lead to acceptance of vasectomy. Fear of surgery, concerns regarding physical weakness, misconceptions about sexual performance, and social stigma were identified as major influencing factors. These findings are consistent with previous studies that reported inadequate knowledge and negative beliefs as significant barriers to the acceptance of male sterilization.

The results also indicated that educational status, prior awareness, number of children, and communication between spouses were associated with participants' attitudes toward vasectomy. Participants with better educational backgrounds and greater exposure to family planning information showed more positive attitudes. This highlights the importance of health education and counselling in improving men's understanding of vasectomy and encouraging shared responsibility in family planning.

The findings emphasize the need for targeted awareness programs, community-based educational interventions, and active involvement of healthcare professionals, particularly nurses, in addressing myths and misconceptions related to vasectomy. Such interventions can contribute to increased acceptance and utilization of vasectomy as a safe and effective method of permanent contraception.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that although awareness regarding vasectomy exists among urban men, misconceptions, fear, and sociocultural beliefs continue to influence their decision-making. The study identified several factors affecting the acceptance of vasectomy, including concerns about masculinity, fear of surgical procedures, lack of accurate information, and social influences.

The findings suggest that improving knowledge through structured educational programs and counselling can positively influence men's attitudes toward vasectomy. Healthcare professionals, especially nurses, play a vital role in promoting awareness and encouraging male participation in family planning services. The development and dissemination of information booklets and educational materials may help reduce misconceptions and support informed decision-making regarding vasectomy.

Therefore, strengthening community awareness programs and promoting shared reproductive responsibility between partners are essential for increasing the acceptance of vasectomy and achieving family planning goals.

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